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A Study on Financial-Literacy of Urban Street Vendors of Umiam, Meghalaya

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Abstract:

Finance has become an essential part of the economy, not only for the national economy, but also for the development of society. Financial literacy is a starting point for sustainable development for individuals, businesses and the economy. The study of socio-economic status and financial literacy among street vendors is crucial in understanding the dynamics of informal economics. Street vending often overlooked, plays a significant role in urban settings, contributing to livelihoods and local economies. The major objective of this investigation is to study their nature of business, income, expenditure and savings. This survey had been conducted to clarify the socio-economic and financial literacy status among the street vendors.

Keywords: Financial literacy, Sustainable development, Socio-Economic status, Street vendor, Finance.

Introduction:

Finance has become an essential part of the economy, not only for the national economy, but also for the development of society. Financial literacy is a starting point for sustainable development for individuals, businesses and the economy. A person can live an independent life only when he is independent in various aspects of his/her life. Viz. social, political, economic, all aspects are related. Economic independence is important in personal as well as collective life as it helps in flourishing the other two. India is one of the developing countries in the world and it stands first in terms of population in the world, hence, our government is not able to give jobs for all people. The urban areas have all the specialty and job opportunities in these settings. Some skilled people try to get the white-collar job in the urban region. The literate and illiterate people have to make self-employment through various aspects including informal sectors. This research article attempts to study about the Street Vendors in Meghalaya. The major objective of this investigation is to study their nature of business, income, expenditure and savings. This survey had been conducted to clarify the socio-economic and financial literacy status among the street vendors.

“**Financial Literacy** is the ability to make informed judgments and to take effective decisions regarding the use and management of money. Financial literacy is therefore a combination of a person’s skills, knowledge, attitudes and ultimately their behaviours in relation to money. **Street Vendors** means a person engaged in vending of articles, goods, wares, food items or merchandise of everyday use or offering services to the general public, in a street, lane, side walk, footpath, pavements, public park or any other public place or private area, from a temporary build up structures or by moving from place to place and includes hawker, peddler, squatter and all other synonymous terms which may be local or region specific.” (The Street Vendors Protection of Livelihood and Regulation of Street Vending Act, 2014). Therefore street vendor refers to those who are unable to get regular jobs in the remunerative formal sector on account of their low level of education and skills. However, street vending is an important activity related to urban areas. They play a significant role in local economics providing convenient access to products and services while often contributing of the vibrancy and diversity of urban areas. According to a National Policy of Street Vendors, 2004 by Government of India street vendors defined as “A person who offers good or services for sell to the

public without having a permanent built of structure or mobile stall”. In this policy document the term urban vendor is inclusive of both-traders and service providers, stationery as well as mobile vendor and incorporates all other locals as howker, pheriwala, footpath dukandars, and sidewalk traders.

Objectives:

1. To analyze the Socio-Economic Status of the Street Vendors.
2. To analyze the Financial Literacy Status of the Street Vendors.

Study Area:

Shillong is the capital of the northeastern state of Meghalaya in India, known as the “Scotland of the East”, embodies a rich cultural diversity and stunning beauty. It’s renowned for its picturesque landscapes, rolling hills and pleasant climate. The city is a melting pot of diverse cultures and traditions, with a vibrant music scene and mix of indigenous KHASI traditions and colonial heritage. Umiam, also called Barapani, is a mesmerizing reservoir located close to Shillong. It’s known for its serene ambience, surrounded by lush greenery and the breathtaking and stunning Umiam Lake. It makes a popular destination for water sports, picnic and leisure activities. The area attracts tourists and locals’ alike, seeking relaxation or tranquility amidst and immersion in nature’s allure or splendor. Mostly, the economic activities are recognized nearby the Lum Neheru Park, Umiam.

Methodology:

This is an empirical and exploratory study based on Primary data. The population of the study covered the markets around Umiam Lake, Meghalaya and data is collected through a simple random sampling procedure. The responses are collected in a structured schedule questionnaire. Researcher has adopted convenience sampling for determining the sample. The schedule questionnaire is consisting of 35 questions. The questionnaire was a mix of open-ended and close-ended questions. Primary data collection through a sample survey involves gathering information directly from a specific group of individuals to understand opinions, behaviours or attitudes. Diagrammatic representation of data has been used to analyze the socio-economic status of the street vendors and the financial literacy of them in the study area. Pie charts, bar diagram and histogram are used to analyze the above two objectives.

Results and Discussions:

Objective 1: To analyze the Socio-Economic Status of Street Vendors-

The Socio-economic landscape of street vendors plays a crucial role in shaping the dynamics of urban environments, contributing to both the local economy and the livelihoods of countless individuals. This report delves into a comprehensive analysis of the social and economic aspects affecting street vendors, shedding light on their living conditions, income levels, and the challenges they face in various urban settings. By examining these factors, we aim to gain a nuanced understanding of the complexities inherent in the lives of street vendors, ultimately providing valuable insights for policymakers, urban planners, and community stakeholders.

In this report, I explore key indicators such as income distribution, access to basic amenities, and the impact of regulatory frameworks on street vendors' economic opportunities. The findings presented herein are based on a comprehensive survey conducted across diverse urban areas, capturing the diversity of challenges faced by street vendors.

Gender distribution: Gender refers to the roles, behaviours, activities, expectations, and societal norms associated with being male or female. It goes beyond the biological differences between men and women and encompasses the socially and culturally constructed attributes and behaviours that a given society considers appropriate for men and women. The gender distribution of urban vendors indicates that males constitute 48%, while females make up 52% in the total distribution. This suggests a slight majority of female vendors in the urban context. Further analysis could explore factors influencing these proportions and their implications for urban economic dynamics.

Age distribution: The age composition of urban street vendors reveals that the majority, with the highest concentration, fall within the age range of 30 to 40. Notably, there are no vendors below the age of 18, implying that street vending is predominantly undertaken by individuals in the 30 to 40 age group. This demographic insight may have implications for understanding the workforce dynamics and economic participation within urban street.

Educational Status: Education is the most crucial factor for the growth of an individual or society and is indispensable for nation building. It imparts knowledge and skill to an individual, thus shaping the character of the individual. It is found that in the study area that most of the respondents have primary and matriculation level of education. We find that the respondents mainly fall under the primary and elementary level of education where highest frequency occur with 43 respondents which constitute of 48% of the entire sample, Secondary/ High school respondents with frequency of 18 respondents which constitute 20% in the total sample, and illiterate, undergraduate and post-graduate respondents with frequency of 15, 9, and 4 which constitute 17%, 10% and 5% in the total sample respectively.

Caste or Social Category: The caste composition analysis of urban street vendors indicates a significant majority from the Scheduled Tribe (ST) category, constituting 62 percent. The General category represents 22 percent, Other Backward Classes (OBC) make up 13 percent, and the Scheduled Caste (SC) comprises 3 percent. This distribution suggests a substantial representation of ST vendors, potentially reflecting socio-economic patterns within urban street vending. Further investigation into the implications of this caste distribution on vendor dynamics and opportunities may provide valuable insights.

Religion Composition: The religion composition among urban street vendors reveals a majority belonging to the Christian community, comprising 59 individuals. Hindus represent 23 people, while Muslims constitute 6 individuals. This distribution suggests religious diversity among street vendors, with a significant Christian presence. Exploring the potential impact of religious composition on vendor interactions and community dynamics could provide further insights into the socio-cultural aspects of urban street vending.

Income Group: The income analysis of urban street vendors indicates that 40 individuals fall within the income range of 5000-10000, while 28 people report an income below 5000. This distribution highlights a substantial portion of vendors earning within the 5000-10000 range, underscoring the economic diversity within the urban street vending community. Further examination could explore factors influencing income disparities and potential avenues for economic empowerment.

Objective 2: To analyze the Financial literacy among the Urban Street Vendors-

To study the scenario of financial literacy among the Urban street vendors, following factors are under consideration for the study.

Financial Inclusion:

Figure 2.1:

Analysis of Financial Inclusion: Among the surveyed urban street vendors, 16 individuals, or approximately 18%, do not have a bank account, while 56 people, constituting around 64%, have access to an ATM. This suggests a notable portion of street vendors may face challenges in formal financial inclusion. The analysis could explore reasons behind not having a bank account, assess barriers to accessing financial services, and examine the impact of these conditions on the ability to secure loans or manage financial resources effectively within the urban street vending context.

Loan Taken:**Table 2.1:**

YES/NO	Loan Taken
YES	33
NO	55

Figure 2.2:

Analysis of taking Loans: A loan gives you access to the cash you need today, and lets you repay those funds over a period of time. In exchange for this convenience, you'll need to pay extra fees in the form of interest. Majority of the population has never taken any kind of loans from banks or other financial institute. The other 37% of the population who has taken the loan are expecting to pay back the amount with their future increase or success in business.

Financial Awareness:**Table 2.2: Financial Awareness**

	YES	NO
Attended	22	66
Calls and messages	25	63
Financial Fraud	29	59
Government Aided Schemes	18	70

Figure 2.3: Financial Awareness

Analysis of Financial Awareness: Only around 30% of the population has ever attended any financial awareness program or received calls and messages regarding financial awareness schemes. Financial fraud among urban street vendors concerning government-aided schemes often involves false promises or misleading information conveyed through calls or messages. In surveyed area 29 people have fallen in such traps. Scammers might pose as government officials, offering fake schemes or asking for personal information, bank details, or fees to enroll in non-existent programs. Government agencies usually communicate official schemes through verified channels, and it's crucial to verify the authenticity of any such communication before sharing personal information or making any payments.

Conclusion:

The survey findings on street vendors social and financial literacy highlight critical areas for improvement. Street vendors exhibit limited understanding in managing finances, accessing financial services, and fostering strong social connections. This lack of literacy in both spheres underscores the potential benefits of targeted educational interventions. Enhancing financial literacy could empower vendors to better manage their income, allocate resources effectively, and access financial tools crucial for business growth. Simultaneously, improving social literacy could aid in establishing stronger community ties, expanding customer networks, and fostering a supportive environment for their businesses.

The correlation between enhanced literacy and improved socio-economic status is evident. By addressing these deficiencies, tailored programs focusing on financial planning, basic business skills, and community engagement could profoundly impact the street vending community. Initiatives that provide practical knowledge and tools tailored to their needs could lead to more resilient businesses and contribute to the socio-economic advancement of street vendors.

Efforts to bridge this literacy gap should be comprehensive, integrating accessible educational resources, workshops, and mentorship programs. Empowering street vendors with these skills could create a ripple effect, leading to more sustainable businesses, economic stability, and greater social inclusion within the street vending community. Overall, this survey highlights a crucial need to invest in educational initiatives geared towards enhancing both social and financial literacy among street vendors for their holistic empowerment and prosperity.

The survey revealed that street vendors lack essential knowledge in managing finances and building social connections. They face challenges in financial planning, accessing services, and nurturing community ties crucial for business growth. Bridging this gap is vital. Educational programs tailored to their needs, focusing on budgeting, basic business skills, and community engagement, could significantly benefit these vendors. Strengthening financial literacy would empower them to handle income better and access necessary resources, while improved social literacy could expand their customer base and create a supportive business environment. Investing in these educational initiatives could foster more resilient businesses, elevate socio-economic status, and promote inclusivity within the street vending community. Ultimately, enhancing social and financial literacy stands as a critical step towards empowering street vendors for sustained success.

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